

Email to invite the authors to participate in the Live Review

From: [Collaborator]
To: [Manuscript's author(s)]

Dear Dr. [NAME OF AUTHOR(S)],

Thank you for submitting your research manuscript to [NAME OF THE JOURNAL]. As part of our commitment to innovation, we are partnering with [PREreview](#) to offer authors an alternative way to have their submissions evaluated by their peers.

Instead of going through our traditional review process, we will team up with PREreview to host and facilitate a [Live Review](#), a 90-minute facilitated Zoom call in which participants will be guided to have a constructive discussion of your manuscript following a collaborative notes document similar to [this one](#).

From the notes, the [INSERT ORGANIZING TEAM NAME] will compose a review and publish it on PREreview.org about 2 weeks after the event. Our team will use the PREreview in our evaluation process. [add language here to make it clear for authors what they should expect to hear back about the manuscript's acceptance if applicable].

As author(s), you are invited to join the call, but it's not a requirement.

If you are interested in participating but want more details, please let us know by [DATE].

Email for the author(s) of the preprint to be Live Reviewed to inform them of what's next

From: PREreview team
To: preprint author(s)
cc: collaborators (e.g., JMIR Publications editors), community@prereview.org

Dear Dr. [NAME OF AUTHOR(S)],

It is a pleasure to e-meet you. Thank you for agreeing to have your manuscript reviewed by a group of peers via PRereview Live Reviews. I'm **[INSERT FACILTATOR'S NAMES & TITLES]** and I will be the call facilitators.

The Live Review of your manuscript is scheduled for **[DATE]** at **[TIME]** and will last 90 minutes. Here is the **REGISTRATION FORM** **[INSERT LINK]**. Please make sure to register if you plan to attend and feel free to share it with your colleagues (here is language you can use in an invitation email).

With this email, I'd like to offer an outline of what is going to happen in preparation for and at the event. **In bold are questions for you we'd appreciate knowing the answers to by [DATE].**

- If you haven't already, please ensure your **manuscript is published on a preprint server and has obtained a digital object identifier (DOI)**. Once that is done, **please share the preprint DOI with us by replying to this email or emailing us at community@prereview.org**.
- At the event, **[INSERT FACILTATOR'S NAMES]** will facilitate the call following a [collaborative notes document similar to this one](#).
- **Do you plan to attend the event?** If you do, here is what you can expect. During the call, we will ask that all authors present please identify themselves by adding the word "author" to their Zoom name. After some housekeeping announcements, we will offer you the mic for a few minutes if you wish to introduce yourself and share questions or point to parts of the manuscript that you most wish to get feedback on (page 4 of the Google doc). Then we will ask you to remain silent (unless a question is specifically directed at you) until the end of the call when we'll ask you if you wish to make any comments on what was just discussed.
- The call will be recorded but the recording will not be shared outside of the PRereview and **[Collaboration Team]**.
- After the call, in collaboration with volunteers from the call, we will put together a review which will be published on [PRereview.org](#). This usually takes 2 weeks.

Please let us know if you have any questions or concerns.

We look forward to it!